

SPEECH IN MOTHER LANGUAGE METHODOLOGY COURSES TEST-TEST IN DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS USING ASSIGNMENTS

Alikhanova Sarvinozkhan daughter of Shukhratkhan

Samarkand vocational school

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Abstract. *This article reviews the effectiveness of tests, tasks and educational games in developing speaking skills in the native language methodology.*

Key words: *speech, thinking, fluency, pronunciation, proficiency, written speech, oral speech, text, assignment.*

INTRODUCTION

Mother tongue education is a skill that allows children to expand their thinking activities, to be able to think freely, to listen to the opinions of others, to be able to express their thoughts fluently orally and in writing, and to communicate freely with members of society. and serves to develop skills. In this place, mother tongue education is considered not as an academic subject, but as an educational process that organizes the entire educational system.

The type of speech activity is the use of thinking based on language tools (words, phrases, sentences). Speech serves as communication and message, expressing one's thoughts with emotions and influencing others.

A well-developed speech serves as one of the important means of human activity in society. For the student, speech is a tool for successful education at school.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

What is speech development? If we take into account the student and the work he has done with the language, speech development means comprehensive active practical mastery of the language. In the case of a teacher, speech development means the use of methods and techniques that help students to actively master the pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure and connected speech of the language.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech: 1) working on words; 2) working on phrases and sentences; 3) work on connected speech.

The indicated three directions are carried out in parallel: vocabulary work provides material for the sentence; working on words, phrases and sentences prepares for connected speech. In turn, connected speech serves as a means of enriching the vocabulary of a story and an essay.

Developing written speech is a more complex process than oral speech. Because it requires students to construct correct sentences in terms of grammar and content, to use each word correctly in its place, to express ideas concisely, coherently, expressively, in terms of style, and to express them fluently. It requires making conclusions based on the ideas made. Another complex nature of this speech is that it has to do with spelling, punctuation, and style. Writing the word correctly, using punctuation marks appropriately, expressing the idea in accordance with the requirements of the style requires a great responsibility from the student. Therefore, this type of speech is rather slow and complex.

Another characteristic of written speech is that it can be checked, corrected, and improved. In this respect, it has more favorable opportunities than oral speech. The student works on mistakes and shortcomings in written speech, eliminates them, tries to avoid these mistakes and shortcomings in his future work.

In the lessons of the mother tongue, the teacher should not forget that often students pay a lot of attention to spelling and punctuation in written works and do not work enough on the content of the text. The texts are often dominated by ideas unrelated to the topic, and the main idea is neglected. That's why in native language classes, students' attention is not only on spelling and punctuation, but also on the fact that the expressed opinion has reasonable arguments, the correct placement of the material, and the correct expression of the opinion in accordance with the speech conditions. should be focused.

It is necessary to create such a situation in mother language lessons that the student is satisfied with the text he created. This inspires him to improve his speech.

If the students think creatively independently and can express the product of their thoughts correctly and fluently in oral and written forms according to the speech conditions, then the native language training has been effective.

Another factor that makes it difficult for the development of students' speech in mother tongue classes is that students speak Tajik, Turkmen, Kyrgyz or other (dialect) at home, on the street, or outside of class, and speak Uzbek at school. it is winter. Ethnographic data show that many Tajiks, Turkmens, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs live in the territory of our republic. Most of them spoke Tajik, Kyrgyz, etc. at home and studied in Uzbek at school. This situation, without a doubt, limits the ability of students to freely express their thoughts using the rich possibilities of language.

In addition to the negative factors listed above, there is a lack of content and content of work conducted in our mother tongue outside of the classroom and school, not always following the uniform mode of speech, and parents' insufficient work on the child's speech, such as the oral and written performance of students. negatively affects the development of speech.

Learning the language in practice involves listening to all the sound units of the native language (sound - syllable - phrase - text) and pronouncing them correctly, therefore, work on the formation of sound pronunciation in a preschool child is regular should be carried out.

Different types of tone, timbre, pause, emphasis are important means of expressiveness of sound.

It is very important to teach the student the correct use of intonation, to build an intonation image of the expressed idea, giving not only the content value, but also emotional characteristics. In parallel with this, depending on the situation, it is necessary to develop the ability to correctly pronounce sounds, words, phrases, and sentences (diction), depending on the situation.

While educating students to pay attention to the intonation aspect of speech, an adult person (pedagogue) develops his ability to listen to speech, to feel timbre (the unique quality of each sound) and weight, to feel the power of sound. which also affects the development of the ability to listen to music in the future.

Work on speech intonation, expressiveness of sound is necessary for children to learn to express their attitude to the expressed idea, based on the text, by raising or lowering their voice, giving logical and emotional emphasis to the spoken text. For this, the pedagogue should use more appropriate tasks. It is these abilities that are necessary for the student to compose different types

of fluent thoughts that require different intonation expressions - to tell a story, to describe, to reason.

While developing the sound aspect of speech, the educator should teach the child to take into account the compatibility of the thoughts with the goals and conditions of communication based on the subject, the topic of expression and the audience.

The pitch of the speech should be appropriate, and the speed should correspond to the surrounding environment and the purpose of the thought. An important indicator of good, correct speech is its fluency.

The integral connection of articulatory and intonation skills implies the formation of listening and articulatory-pronunciation skills in a broad sense.

In the process of work, the teacher should be able to listen and identify the sound structure of the word, the place of stress in the word, develop a sense of rhyme and weight, give accurate pronunciation, various intonation descriptions of words, phrases, sentences. It is necessary to use exercises that help to form the ability.

Formation of these complex speech skills requires repetition of phonetic exercises and their regular practice.

While distinguishing the priorities of work on each speech task, it should be noted that all of them participate in interdependence and close cooperation.

On the basis of the growth and development of fluent speech lies the ability to use various means of communication (between words, sentences, parts of the text), to form ideas about the structure of various types of texts - description, description, reasoning.

In the development of the dictionary, work on the content of the word comes first, because it is the semantic selection of words in accordance with the text (revealing the content of polysemous words, synonymic and antonymic comparisons) of language and speech phenomena. forms awareness.

In the process of mastering the grammatical structure of speech, learning the ways of forming words in different parts of speech, forming language generalizations, as well as constructing syntactic structures (simple and compound sentences) are the main tasks.

In training the sound culture of speech, it is necessary to pay more attention to work on intonation expressiveness, tempo, pronunciation and fluency of expressing thoughts, because the formation of fluent speech is based on these skills.

The teacher should teach children to connect sentences in parallel, in which the sentences are not connected to each other, but compared or even contrasted (There was a strong wind. The rabbit hid in the nest). When teaching students to compose fluent texts, it is necessary to pay special attention to the development of their ability to reveal the topic and the main idea of the spoken word, to put a title on the text.

Intonation plays a big role in the organization of fluent thought, therefore, the formation of the skill of using the intonation of certain sentences helps to note the structural unity and completeness of the text as a whole. The joint creation of words by the teacher and the student is the main condition for the development of monologic speech. The teacher should support the initiative of the student by asking guiding and clarifying questions, creating game situations. The pedagogue quietly tells the content of the story, the plan, the possible development of the events, the form of words is important in the joint creation of words.

According to the methods of transmitting information or its presentation, the following types of opinions can be distinguished: description, description, reasoning, opinions can be found in a contaminated (mixed) form, that is, in them, the methods of description (reflection) are added to the statement (and vice versa).

It is recommended to teach different types of texts in the form of conversation, analysis (evaluation) of one's own and others' text, making a plan and telling a story about it, using a text scheme (model), various exercises.

The development of a student's speech is a complex process, and the factors hindering it do not depend only on the content of education or the teacher. The process of teaching to express thoughts correctly and fluently orally and in writing will be easy only if all possibilities are used to the fullest. It opens a wide way for the development of the student's speech.

As we know, students get bored with sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to use various methods and games, interesting methods, to develop their speech. Below are some of them as examples.

"Chain" The teacher writes a few words on the blackboard. For example: Nafisa, clock, rain, book. Students independently make sentences based on these words.

"Interdependence" Picture cards are distributed to students. After they get acquainted with the cards, the student talks about the object in the picture. For example: "This is an apple. The apple grows in the garden and is included in the fruits. The students like it very much." zara should say it depends.

For example: "This is the sun. When the sun rises, the air warms up. The students love it. When the sun warms, apples and other fruits ripen." must find the connection between the subject. The game continues in this order.

"Looking for commonality" Make a circle with the reader. The leader throws the ball to the students and says two unrelated words. For example: school and student, book and shelf, sun and flower... The student who catches the ball returns the ball by saying the common sign between the pairs of words.

"Safag" Pupils are given a task to find their way from school or home to a certain place. Pupils independently observe the "object" for several days and describe it verbally. This game, which requires carefulness, diligence, observation, and attention to the environment, can foster feelings of love for the Motherland, love for nature, and attention to the environment. In addition, when using this game, the student's speech develops, vocabulary increases, and independent thinking skills are formed.

The above-mentioned educational game serves to increase the activity of the students in the classroom, to facilitate and strengthen the process of mastering knowledge, and to organize interesting activities aimed at developing speech.

The idea of empowering our society is expressed directly in the educational process, it is provided on the basis of its new organization and content change, more humanization, socialization and democratization.

"Payrovlar" game. Through this game, phrases and proverbs gradually enter the students' speech. Examples of folk oral creativity, such as phrases and proverbs, increase the effectiveness of our speech. Pre-selected phrases or proverbs are given to the small group to play the game at the beginning of the lesson. it will be very appropriate.

For example:

1. You can't speak loudly.
2. A tooth gives sustenance.
3. What is pressure on the teeth?
4. He kept it in the socket of his tooth.

The "carpet of ideas" method is one of the factors of increasing the level of written speech literacy. Pupils create new words from the word tree prepared by the teacher or, if not, create new words through additions using the "Butterfly" method. words are created and the correct spelling of that word is ensured. For example: book, reader, book lover, books, in the book, from the book...

The student writes his thoughts consistently and without mistakes through generalized concepts, words with differences in pronunciation and spelling are explained.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to create such an environment of education in which the student feels that he is a person and feels the attention towards him. if he gives, if he gains confidence in his own strength and talent, the improved learning process will occur by itself. A source of educational communication is created, defined by openness, mutual cooperation of participants, equality of evidence, collaborative knowledge bank, mutual evaluation and control. Therefore, the teacher himself should constantly work on himself, continuously improve his pedagogical skills, improve the educational process by creatively using the world and national pedagogical heritage and scientific achievements.

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